

Introducing the INDUSAC Project: Bridging the Gap Between Academic Knowledge and Industry Practice

By Urška Mrgole, Marjeta Trobec, Duško Odić, Jožef Stefan Institute

INDUSAC, a three-year-long Horizon Europe project, started in September 2022. INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, industry-academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation (Figure 1), by extending the usual company-researcher partnerships to students. The mechanism's two main components were developed in the project's first year: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles to foster the industry-academia collaboration, and an online platform to support the methodology¹ (Figure 2). In 2023, public universities, companies, students and researchers were invited to join INDUSAC through three open calls: the open call for universities to promote INDUSAC opportunities among students and researchers, the open call for companies to provide challenges and the open call for students and researchers to solve company challenges. The

idea behind INDUSAC is to bring together companies and their challenges on one hand and on the other, an international team of 3-6 students and/or researchers to solve a company challenge within 4-8 weeks. The co-creation teams must be composed of at least three participants from three different countries and at least two genders must be represented in the co-creation team to ensure geographical and gender balance.

Figure 1: The INDUSAC project design from start to finish (Source: the INDUSAC project information leaflet)

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In the initial call (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-20: *Piloting a new industry-academia knowledge exchange focusing on companies' needs (CSA)*) within which INDUSAC received funding, special emphasis was given to students and researchers from widening countries. Consequently, also in INDUSAC special focus is on widening countries, with the target being that at least 60% of co-creation team members are from widening countries.

The piloting begins when a company provides a challenge in a pre-defined form based on nine different possible types of challenges, and it continues with co-creation teams that provide solutions in the form of pre-defined types of deliverables specific to the type of challenge, which are then evaluated by companies². Once the solution to the challenge is approved by the company, each student member of the co-creation team receives up to 1000 EUR gross per solved challenge in the form of financial support to third parties (FSTP).

Figure 2: Schematic view of the INDUSAC project (Source: <https://indusac.eu/>) indicating that the methodology and the platform support the co-creation process.

² Odić D, U Mrgole, M Trobec. 2024. Feasibility analysis for the new mechanism of knowledge transfer within the INDUSAC project. In: 17th International Technology Transfer Conference: 9 October 2024, Ljubljana, Slovenia: Information Society - IS 2024: Proceedings of the 27th international multiconference E: 39-42

The co-creation team members (students and researchers) receive a questionnaire before the start and after the finish of the co-creation project. Team members provide feedback on how the collaboration affects social impact, how their competencies have increased and how appropriate the funding is. Companies on the other hand give feedback on the quality of work performed by the students/researchers, the impact that their work has and their satisfaction with the results provided by the team³. Further updates of the Methodology are foreseen based on the feedback from participants (companies and students & researchers).

Achievements and results

The first co-creation projects have started in March 2024. By the beginning of December 2024, we gathered 195 challenges, supported 38 co-creation teams and distributed 69,000 EUR to students as FSTP funds.

Feedback collected so far shows that INDUSAC is complying with/exceeding most KPIs and objectives, overachieving in some specific ones (e.g. number of followers, etc.): 1. At least 70% of participating students and researchers have at least one core professional transversal and entrepreneurial skill having been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC mechanism → so far 87% of

³ Odić D, U Mrgole, M Trobec. 2024. Feasibility analysis for the new mechanism of knowledge transfer within the INDUSAC project. In: 17th International Technology Transfer Conference: 9 October 2024, Ljubljana, Slovenia: Information Society - IS 2024: Proceedings of the 27th international multi-conference E: 39-42

At least 70% of the participating students and researchers report that at least one core professional transversal and entrepreneurial skill has been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC mechanism.

So far, 87% of the students and researchers reported that negotiation and conflict management skills have been significantly developed through participating in the co-creation project.

At least 70% of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) report that the solution(s) delivered by the co-creation quick intervention was highly relevant to their company and contributed to overcoming the challenge that was identified by them (and which was accepted by the program as being suitable).

So far, 77% of the companies reported their overall satisfaction with the solutions developed.

At least 80% of students and SME staff state that it is likely or highly likely they would recommend participation in such a programme to their peers.

So far, 89% of students stated that they are likely or highly likely to recommend participation in the programme to their peers.

students and researchers reporting Negotiation and Conflict management skills having been significantly developed. 2. At least 70% of SMEs reporting that the solution(s) delivered by the co-creation quick intervention were highly relevant to their company and contributed to overcoming the challenge that was identified by them (and which was accepted by the program as being suitable) → so far 77% of companies report the overall satisfaction with the solutions. 3. At least 80% of students and SME staff stating that it is likely or highly likely they would recommend participation in such a programme to their peers → so far 89% of students stated that they are likely or highly likely to recommend participation in the programme to their peers.

The feedbacks highlight also that students and researchers derive significant benefits from engaging in collaborative work with companies and participating in international team projects. This hands-on experience during the co-creation initiative not only enhances their practical skills but also fosters a deeper understanding of real-world working. These collaborative interactions are fundamental to achieving one of the primary goals of the INDUSAC project, which seeks to bridge academic knowledge with industry practice.

Testimonials from participants (students and companies)

Muhammad from Finland

We're very grateful to INDUSAC for being accepted for one of the interesting projects regarding the sustainability of the environment. As well as to (a company from Slovenia) for cooperation and providing enough information which helped us reach the final solution and gave us an insight of working with industry.

Alex from Hungary

It was a great pleasure to take part in the INDUSAC co-creation project. As a member of the international team together with the professional from the leading company, I had the ability not only to apply the knowledge and to use the skills I gained while studying but also to develop myself in terms of global teamwork and solving genuine business problems. I am truly privileged to be able to participate in something like that and I would like to encourage.

A company from Slovenia

I believe the INDUSAC project is highly beneficial to both the company and the co-creation team, as it effectively bridges the gap between universities/institutes and SME's like ours. Chapeau!

Lali from Georgia

Participating in the INDUSAC co-creation project was one of the most incredible experiences I've had. I am grateful for the opportunity to be part of this international initiative while collaborating with students from various countries and backgrounds. We had the chance to develop our perspectives and insights while working towards shared goals. It was a fantastic experience, and I am eager to participate in other projects!

A company from Austria

The INDUSAC Team was an interesting experience for us to get an external view on our production technology and the market for nanoscaled products behind. The team was doing this task in a good way using the knowledge of students from different disciplines.

Conclusion

The INDUSAC project is set to develop a mechanism to promote industry-academia collaboration that would benefit all parties involved. Companies benefit in the form of creative young minds (and potential future employees), satisfactory results and useful solutions. Students benefit in the form of increased competencies from various fields, first contact with companies (potential employers) and financial awards. Researchers benefit from working with students (potential future co-workers) and working with companies (direct contact for future research cooperation). The feedback gathered so far, alongside testimonials from all involved, complements the developed mechanism and demonstrates that the INDUSAC mechanism shows promising results with regard to bolstering knowledge transfer.

Three questions with...

Urška Mrgole and **Marjeta Trobec**,
MSc, INDUSAC project coordinator
from Jožef Stefan Institute in
Ljubljana, Slovenia

1. On a global level, what is your view on the Code of Practice on Industry-Academia Co-Creation? What is the value of having such a document?

The Code of Practice emphasises the importance of entrepreneurial skills and practices. It fosters the use of interactive models and digital platforms for improved knowledge sharing in industry-academia collaboration. INDUSAC tackles all the aspects mentioned above. It is important that the European Commission (EC) provides a baseline and guidance for additional or improved national and international measures that lead towards knowledge valorisation. In Slovenia, for example, knowledge transfer offices are now supported more systematically. For EU-wide co-creation mechanisms that have proven their effectiveness (as the one developed in INDUSAC), it is important to keep developing the network of participating/supporting organisations further, to maintain such mechanisms in the long run and to leverage the synergies of complementary mechanisms.

2. How would you describe the nature of the co-creation projects promoted by INDUSAC?

Within INDUSAC, companies and co-creation teams work on concrete, real-life cases, which are to be resolved within four to eight weeks. Given this short implementation time, these are not so much the type of research and development projects that generate classical research papers. Co-creation projects within INDUSAC are more of an entry point for future cooperation between researchers and companies. Wide inclusiveness is one of the main advantages of INDUSAC: companies of all sizes and from all sectors can participate and connect with students and researchers from various study and research fields for future cooperation.

3. In the INDUSAC open calls for students and researchers, you ask that 60% of members of the co-creation teams must be from Widening countries. Where do you think we stand with industry-academia collaboration in these countries?

As mentioned, special emphasis was given to students and researchers from Widening countries already in the call under which INDUSAC receives funding. Consequently, this special focus has been an integral part of the strategic project set-up from the very beginning. In terms of contract collaboration, we believe that there are not so many differences between Widening and other EU countries. There are, however, stronger differences when it comes to the founding of spin-outs and spin-offs. The reason behind this might be that the entrepreneurial spirit and mindset are not yet as strongly developed in Widening countries as in other EU member states.

“ We can say it loud and clear: only by working together—start-ups, universities, research organisations, SMEs, and industry—can we address the East-West divide and strengthen Europe as a whole. Collaboration is the key to achieving this. ”

We sat down with Markus von Gemmingen-Hornberg from Siemens AG, Research & Innovation Ecosystem, to discuss and hear more about the development of the Code of Practice, his perspective as an industry representative in industry-academia collaborations, and key considerations in intellectual asset management.

European IP Helpdesk: When discussing knowledge transfer, the significance of large organisations cannot be underestimated. In this regard, we see that Siemens Research & Innovation Ecosystem (RIE) has consistently played an active role in advancing these efforts. Could you tell us a bit more about this particular department, its objectives and specific function within the company?

Markus von Gemmingen: Our department, Research and Innovation Ecosystems, operates with a global mandate, and we all share the belief that collaborating with external innovation partners is essential for achieving better tech. For more than two decades, Siemens AG has actively engaged under a dedicated scheme with universities to foster this collaboration. But what do we mean by "better tech"? We believe that solutions, innovations, and the development of new talent for the Industrial Metaverse, Cybersecurity, Generative AI, Electronics etc. can only be achieved when working

together with external partners in innovation. As a small group, our department with a global presence, is dedicated to supporting and enabling collaboration with the external research world with the objective of creating "technology with purpose"—meaningful, impact-focused activities. With our mandate, we strive to work "outside-in" with the best external innovation partners available to us as a company.

